

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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THE MAIN ROLE OF THE TEACHER WHILE MANAGING THE CLASSROOM AND SOME ASPECTS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

Nilufar Turdiyeva

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Abstract: Today English teachers of higher educations should be creative, searchable and find the best suitable method for each group or even for each student. In this article there are given some modern methods of teaching English. It describes the role of the teacher in classroom management and the correct use of language for a number of functions in the classroom, some problems and shortcomings of the educational process. It is also highlighted the ways of focusing on a new language and using presentation techniques.

Key words: Target language, classroom management, quality of education, interactive methods, approach, method, language learner, multilingual, direct method, suggestopedia, lexical approach, structural approach.

Annotatsiya: Bugungi kunda oliy ta'limning ingliz tili o'qituvchilari ijodkor, izlanuvchan bo'lishi va har bir guruh yoki har bir narsa uchun eng mos uslubni topishi kerak. Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o'rgatishning ba'zi zamonaviy usullari keltirilgan. Unda o'qituvchining sinfni boshqarishdagi o'rni va sinfdagi qator vazifalarni bajarishda tildan to'g'ri foydalanish, ta'lim jarayonining ayrim muammo va kamchiliklari yoritilgan. Shuningdek, yangi tilga e'tibor qaratish va taqdimot usullaridan foydalanish yo'llari ta'kidlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: Maqsadli til, sinf boshqaruvi, ta'lim sifati, interfaol metodlar, yondashuv, metod, til o'rganuvchi, ko'p tilli, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri metod, suggestopedia, leksik yondashuv, a strukturach.

Аннотация: Сегодня преподаватели английского языка вузов должны быть творческими, поисковыми и находить наиболее подходящий метод для каждой группы или даже для каждого студента. В этой статье приведены некоторые современные методы преподавания английского языка. Описана роль учителя в управлении классом и правильном использовании языка для выполнения ряда функций на уроке, некоторые проблемы и недостатки образовательного процесса. Также выделены способы сосредоточения внимания на новом языке и использования презентационных приемов.

Ключевые слова: Целевой язык, управление классом, качество образования, интерактивные методы, подход, метод, изучающий язык, многоязычие, прямой метод, суггестопедия, лексический подход, структурный подход.

At the present stage of development of higher professional education, there is a tendency to reduce the number of classroom hours and increase the hours allocated for independent work of students. In this regard, we can state the fact that today the role of the teacher in the educational process is being transformed. Until recently, the teacher was perceived as the main source of information, but today his role can be more fully characterized as the organizer and leader, expert and consultant of the educational and self-educational activities of future specialists.

Higher education instruction in English in non-English speaking countries is a reality in different contexts. Higher education institutions promote the adoption of English as a language of instruction to achieve varying objectives, such as internationalization of students and staff; improvement of the English level of the students, etc. This policy towards the adoption of English as language of medium of instruction (EMI) has led to a situation in which students cope with learning content in a language different from their mother tongue and teaching staff having to deliver their courses and/or lectures in English, which is not their first language in many cases. Coping with this change and the resulting difficulties is found in the literature, as Kalmar & Linder state: "Although the shift to teaching in English has often been welcomed by teachers and students, the research community is only beginning to understand the dynamics of these changes within the learning environment.

Such transformations became possible due to the emergence and widespread introduction of innovative and more effective technologies, forms and means of education into the educational process of higher

education, which make it possible to optimize the process of professional training of future specialists as part of their studies at the university.

The high productivity and efficiency of innovative technologies in the context of training future specialists is justified by their multifunctionality. Thus, innovative pedagogical technologies perform the following functions in the educational process: informative; formative; motivating; systematizing; controlling¹.

Innovative technologies and teaching methods make it possible to achieve the following goals: accessibility of the perception of educational material; systematization of knowledge; development of creative abilities of students; self-education; removing the psychological barrier (fear of communicating, making a mistake); comprehension of educational material, analysis of learned material

To effective innovative pedagogical technologies that can be used in the system of teaching English in higher education with a high level of effectiveness in achieving educational results, researchers most often include interactive distance learning technologies (Skype, Viber, WhatsApp, e-mail, Internet chat, etc.), computer learning tools (electronic manuals, textbooks, sources of virtual libraries, educational portals, etc.), multimedia learning resources, training and testing and other latest information technologies.

Tangible progress regarding the effectiveness of teaching English both in the humanities and in technical universities, according to researchers, has been achieved through the widespread use of electronic learning tools in the educational process of higher education. These tools are used both in the classroom and extracurricular (distance) learning.

The didactic potential of electronic teaching aids in English classes lies in the fact that their use in the educational process contributes to:

- better assimilation of knowledge by students;
- the formation and development of various types of skills and abilities (listening skills based on adapted and authentic sound texts, the ability to reproduce monologue and dialogic speech, the skills and abilities of translation and summarizing texts, skills and reading skills with the direct use of materials from the Internet and local networks;
- increasing the informative richness and visibility of the lesson;
- expansion of active and passive dictionaries of students, familiarization with the vocabulary of modern English, which reproduces the culture of a certain country, its political and social structure;
- formation of creativity, development of creative activity of future specialists;
- the formation of motivation for the cognitive activity of students, the need to use a foreign language in interactive communication;
- strengthening the motivation of independent work of students;
- increasing the level of individualization and differentiation of students' activities;
- the ability to choose the pace and volume of educational material, the level of its complexity, to implement control with feedback and diagnostics, to increase the level of its objectivity.

At the present stage, the leading information technology, the means of which are used in almost all spheres of human life, is the Internet. Internet resources not only provide a number of additional means of implementing interpersonal and international communication, but also provide new opportunities in the field of education.

What are teacher roles? Teachers need to behave in different ways at different stages of a lesson to manage the classroom and to successfully guide learners through the lesson. These different ways of behaving in and managing the class are called teacher roles. Teachers adopt (use) a number of different roles in every lesson. Teacher roles vary depending on the teaching approach (way of teaching) used and on the teachers' and learners' preferred learning styles and learning needs.

The teacher roles we adopt have to be appropriate for the teaching and learning context, the teaching approach, the lesson aims, the stage of the lesson the type of activity and the age, level and attitude of the learners. A teacher using a PPP approach will, for example, at different times of the lesson, act as a controller, a model and a guide. However, these teacher roles are not so appropriate for a teacher using a communicative approach. Teacher roles more suitable for a communicative approach include facilitator, resource provider of language, prompter. When learners arrive late in class, the teacher needs to deal with the situation appropriately to ensure that the learners understand that this is not acceptable behavior. In this situation, the teacher's role is primarily to maintain discipline. On the other hand, the teacher adopts inappropriate roles, this can have a negative effect on their classroom management. Imagine a situation where one learner is dominating the interaction in the classroom, resulting in other learners becoming annoyed and being unwilling to participate (take part in something). If the teacher lets the learner continue in a dominating role, he or she could lose the respect of the other students and will be less able to facilitate (make easier) their learning. However, if the teacher sets

¹ Hattier MA. Factor analysis and cut-off scores for the Autism Spectrum Disorder-Observation for children [dissertation] Louisiana State University; 2014.

out clear classroom routines and codes of conduct in which learners take turns to participate and listen to each other's contributions, he or she will build rapport with the class and provide the learners with a more supportive learning environment. There are several common situations in which a teacher has to adapt his or her role as appropriate to encourage smooth classroom management. These include learners not completing homework, monitoring, learners during pair and group activities, learners failing to understand instructions, learners chatting during pair or group work and not focusing on the task. The roles that teachers adopt also depend on the needs of the learners. With young learners, we might take on the role of a parent or a friend when a young student is unwell or unhappy. With teenage or adult learners, two of the key teacher roles are those of motivating students and maintaining discipline (establishing a clear system of rules and codes of behavior). With adult students the teacher's roles are often those of facilitator, language resource and diagnostician.

Key concepts and the language teaching classroom

- What we say, how we say it and what we do make our teacher roles clear to learners. When planning lessons, it is useful to first identify the roles we are going to take on during the lesson and the to think about what we are going to say and do to convey that role clearly to the class.
- It takes practice and experience to know which teacher roles are appropriate with which classes and for which activities. Less experienced teachers may feel comfortable using a limited number of roles at first and then gradually extending their range.
- Some problems with classroom discipline, classroom management and facilitating learning are a result of teachers not adopting appropriate teacher roles.
- Learners take time to get used to the teacher working in different roles. For example, learners who are more familiar with a teacher in the role of manager might be confused by a teacher who takes on the role of facilitator. It is useful to provide some learner training and to introduce the new roles slowly so that learners get used to new ways of working. It is important to be flexible in teacher roles. Sometimes roles need to be changed because of circumstances in the lesson. For example, when we are monitoring a task and realize that learners have not understood the key language, we take on the role of language resource to clarify the language point so that learners can continue with the task. It is sometimes necessary to take on roles we do not always feel comfortable with. When learners do not complete homework tasks, for example, teachers have to be firmer in managing the learners than they usually are. The ability to take on appropriate roles in class is important for establishing class rapport and maintaining a positive and effective learning environment in the classroom.

How do we use language appropriately for classroom functions? Classroom functions are the purposes for which we use language in the classroom. These functions are many and varied, for example explaining and instructing. For each classroom function there are different exponents we can use. The choice of exponent depends on the learning context and purpose, the learners' needs, their age and level. When we choose language that is right for the situation and our audience, we say that we use language appropriately.

Let's look at some of the functions and exponents of teacher language in the sample in detail.

- **Getting learners' attention.** "Stand up, Adam", "Stand up, Evi". The teacher is getting the learners' attention at the beginning of the sequence. The teacher wants everyone to listen and wants Adam and Evi to stand up. There are different times in a lesson when we need to get the learners' attention, for example, when we close an activity or when we want learners to look at the board. We usually keep these utterances short, and very often teachers develop their different classes.

- **Instructing.** OK, Adam will ask and Evi will answer. / read this one.

/look at Adam /Brenda, look at Shona /Look at each other when you ask questions.

The teacher gives learners instructions throughout the teaching sequence: before they start, during the activity (the instructions at this point are about non-linguistic behavior) and at the end as a reminder. The language of instructions often uses the imperative, even with higher-level / older learners.

- **Modelling.** Welcome / May I borrow your pencil, please?

The teacher models (gives a clear example of the target language) at two points in this teaching sequence. It is important, when we model language orally, that we say only what we want learners to repeat, as the teacher does here. In the first example Brenda (the learner) repeats the word welcome after the teacher has said it. In the second example, the teacher provides a model of the structure for the whole class, but they don't repeat it immediately.

In this teaching sequence the modelling is oral. We also model language in writing. We can guess that there is a written model on the board in this teaching sequence as the teacher says read this one.

- **Encouraging and instructing.** Now come on, Evi. / Brenda, a bit louder. Learners are often lacking in confidence and shy about speaking in front of the class. We can encourage them by using language

which makes them feel positive about what they can do and which reduces their level of anxiety. We sometimes also have to tell them what to do (instructing).

- **Nominating.** Oh er, Shona (pause) and (pause) Brenda (pause).

This is just one example of nominating (choosing and naming one learner to speak or do a particular task) in this teaching sequence. We use learners' names for a number of reasons, for example to get their attention, to make them feel we know who they are, to make sure that different learners answer.

- **Prompting a learner to continue.** Come on, Shona, ask...

Prompting (helping learners think of ideas or remember a word or phrase or what to do) can sometimes be quite similar to encouraging. When we prompt we provide words, phrases, ideas or even time to help the learner continue or remember what to say. This means we sometimes leave our utterance unfinished for the learner to finish it for us as in this example.

There is a range of different exponents for each classroom function. The exponents that teachers choose depend on the context, age and language level of the learners and the formality or informality of the teaching situation. The exponents that teacher use must always be appropriate for the situation.

Most of the time, teachers are able to communicate their message successfully to the learners using the target language, accompanied by gestures where appropriate. However, in some situations, particularly with young learners and with beginner or elementary learners, it may be necessary for the teacher to use the mother tongue or LI from time. These situations include:

- Problems with discipline. For example, the teacher needs to quickly stop a situation from getting out of control.
- Possible injury or danger to a learner, for example the teacher notices that a learner's chair is broken.
- Looking after a learner, for example a learner is very upset for personal reasons.
- Repeating instructions in LI after they have been given in the target language, for example with a beginner young learner group.
- Checking understanding of more abstract vocabulary, for example with an advanced class.

It is not a good idea for teachers to use more LI in the classroom than is necessary. If they do, learners can become more unwilling to use the target language because they are used to hearing (and perhaps using) LI.

Another way of focusing on new language is through Test-teach-test. In this, the teacher first gives learners a task that requires them to use target language. If this activity shows that the students don't know how to use the target language, the teacher will then present the new language, then give the students another task to practice the new language. If the first task shows that the students already know the target language sufficiently well, the teacher will move on to something else.

You can see that all the presentation techniques contextualize target language i.e. they put the language in a context which shows its meaning. The context can be provided by building a situation, using a listening or reading text, doing a task, using realia, mime (using the body and no words to convey meaning). When learners learn target language they need to know what it means. Contextualizing aims to help learners to notice and understand meaning. While all the techniques focus on the meaning of the target language they may not all focus so much on its form. For example, PPP and guided discovery focus on form and meaning, whereas task-based presentations focus more on meaning.

Bibliography:

1. David Myers. Social Psychology. 5th int. edition. St. Petersburg - 2000, 684 p.
2. M.M. Bakhtin. Aesthetics of verbal creativity. Moscow "Art" 1979, 420 p.
3. Paul Soper. Fundamentals of the art of speech. Foreign Literature Publishing House. Moscow. 1968 -471 s.
4. Fuad Mammadov. Culturology. Printing house of the company "Abilov, Zeynalov and Sons" Baku. 2002 534 p.
5. Anna Brusser. Methodical recommendations and practical tasks for novice teachers. Moscow 2008, 112 p. –VTsKhT ("I enter the world of arts").
6. Edited by Ph.D. L.A. Vvedenskaya. "Russian language and culture of speech". Moscow, RAGS publishing house. 2005, 581 p.
7. V.A. Maslova Linguoculturology. Moscow. Publishing Center "Academy" -2010, 202 p.
8. Mary Spratt, Alan Pulverness, Melanie Williams "English for speakers of other languages".

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